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Executive Summary

This deliverable presents the deployment and validation of the 3PhaseInsight data pipelines and data apps, demonstrating the functionality, scalability, and practical applicability of the proposed framework. It introduces the open-source, cloud-compatible architecture, detailing its modular pipeline design, core components, and supporting libraries that enable flexible, interoperable data processing.

The document also showcases a set of implemented data apps, including their interfaces and use cases, highlighting usability and value for low-voltage (LV) grid operations. A real-world deployment at Radius and additional services, such as the Phase Connection Assistant along with its associated interfaces, are also presented, demonstrating the framework's operational readiness.

Furthermore, the deliverable addresses deployment strategies and interoperability considerations, emphasising adaptability to different environments, integration with new data sources, and extensibility for future functionalities. The results demonstrate that the framework supports scalable, data-space-compliant deployments and provides a robust foundation for continuous data ingestion and advanced analytics in evolving energy system contexts. Limitations and future research directions are also presented, highlighting the potential to validate the framework across diverse test scenarios involving different datasets and technology stacks. Also, integration with data spaces, especially the energy data space, is a relevant future direction.

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1 Introduction

1.1 Project background

The rapid electrification of the grid is placing more pressure on distribution networks, where increasing numbers of heat pumps, electric vehicles (EVs), and other power electronic devices introduce additional loads and often phase imbalance. At the same time, Danish distribution system operators (DSOs) generally lack detailed observability of low-voltage (LV) grids: topology records might have errors, phase-connection information is often dependent on the communication form of the meters and missing for some meters, and power quality monitoring is limited or absent at secondary substations. This lack of granular, per-phase visibility forces DSOs to rely on conservative planning assumptions, leading to unnecessary capacity buffers, delayed customer connections, and costly reinforcement measures that slow down the green transition. Motivated by these challenges, the 3PhaseInsight project unlocks the value of per-phase smart-meter measurements by developing advanced analytics and scalable data-processing pipelines. The platform validates on a dataset of around 100,000 customers provided by Radius, a leading DSO in Denmark, demonstrating real-world performance at scale and establishing a proven foundation for broader deployment. The central idea is that modern smart meters can provide per-phase voltage, power, and harmonic information at a granularity that enables a new level of LV situational awareness. The platform delivers actionable insights through state-of-the-art data-driven and machine-learning algorithms, directly supporting more efficient operation, planning, and stakeholder-level data sharing.

The project focuses on developing and validating a suite of “data apps” including per-phase topology correction, imbalance screening, and detection of significant electrification loads, such as heat pumps and EV chargers. These analytics are integrated into an open-source, cloud-deployable data-pipeline framework that supports scalable execution, modular workflow composition, and interoperability with DSO environments. By combining improved LV observability with replicable digital tools, the project aims to help DSOs target interventions more precisely, design new customer-facing services, and establish a pathway for broader sector adoption and future expansion of the analytics toolbox.

1.2 Scope of the document

The purpose of the apps is to enhance LV grid observability, support DSO planning and operations, and enable new service concepts through a scalable, open-source data-pipeline architecture. The project demonstrates feasibility and value on a large dataset of real customers, ensuring that the results are grounded in realistic LV conditions. In line with the narrowed focus, these apps are not designed to replace full power-system models, detailed power-quality instrumentation, or real-time operational tools. They do not guarantee full ground-truth accuracy in every topology element, nor can they resolve all harmonics or transient phenomena that require specialised measurement hardware. Their performance depends on the data availability, completeness, and quality of smart-meter data; limitations such as sparse metadata or unmonitored customers can reduce accuracy or prevent validation. Furthermore, the apps are developed as prototypes, meaning that integration into production-grade DSO systems, continuous real-time ingestion, and large-scale automation fall outside the immediate project scope. Despite these limitations, the tools provide the foundation for further development and sector-wide adoption, especially when combined with follow-up stakeholder engagement and expansion of the analytics toolbox. Some of the insights to guide future project take-offs are summarised in D1.2 [1].

This deliverable covers the `cloud-compatible open-source platform`¹ for deploying the data apps described in D1.1 [2], selected implementations in D3.1 [3], and their associated algorithms in D3.2 [4]. The deliverable also advances the data infrastructure described in D2.2 [5] by demonstrating its realisation as a fully `open-source platform`.

¹Also referred to as an `open-source platform` or just the `platform` in this document. The definitions of terms are attached in Appendices

2 The 3PhaseInsight Open-Source Platform

The open-source platform (or the `cloud-compatible platform`) is built to run Data Apps efficiently and at scale, and to expose manageable endpoints for these data apps to create usable services for key players. The platform's architecture implements a flexible adapter pattern for ingesting data from different sources, and an orchestration layer for starting, scheduling and observing the workflows that process it. These workflows store their data as relational data in a database or as files in object storage, and make their results available through an API layer (see D2.2 [5]). The platform's containerised deployment enables data ownership, offering the flexibility to run self-hosted or with different cloud providers.

2.1 Platform Architecture

The open-source `data-platform`², can be divided into a few logical groups presented in Figure 1.

- The **infrastructure** layer consists of a PostgreSQL database alongside object storage (S3-compatible or Azure Blob Storage).
- The **backend** is powered by an Airflow scheduler and worker together with a Dask cluster (scheduler and workers); the Airflow worker delegates the heavy distributed computation to the Dask cluster by submitting task graphs to it. A Redis instance serves as the message broker that the Airflow scheduler uses to dispatch tasks to the workers.
- The **frontend** is the Airflow webserver, which provides a web interface for orchestrating and monitoring workflows (DAGs). Finally, a FastAPI application exposes endpoints that make results queryable by any consumer that meets the authentication requirements.

Data is ingested through a custom adapter that runs as an Airflow DAG, and can be provided in several ways—through an API, FTP, local file storage, and others. Ingested time-series data is stored as partitioned and sharded Parquet files in object storage, while topology data is loaded into the relational database, enabling the `platform` to support complex queries.

The `platform` runs *Data Apps*: workflows that compute results from the stored data. Airflow DAGs provide mechanisms for triggering, scheduling, and monitoring their execution, and Data Apps can be chained within a DAG to form a `pipeline` of several apps that produce more advanced results or a complete `service`.

Data-app output is handled in one of two ways. Intermediate results that are not exposed publicly are kept in object storage or the database. Results intended for consumers are written to a dedicated `run_result` table, which the API serves when its endpoint is called.

2.2 Design choices of the platform

Figure 2 provides a high-level overview of the platform's current design choices and how its components interact across the data lifecycle. It illustrates the flow from data ingestion (CSV sources) through the adapter layer and ingestion DAGs into persistent storage, where time-series data is stored as Parquet files in object storage and metadata and topology are maintained in PostgreSQL. The figure

²<https://github.com/3PhaseInsight/data-platform>

Figure 1: 3PhaseInsight platform architecture

further highlights how Data Apps, services, or custom-developed DAGs can also be integrated with Dask for scalable computation, while downstream interfaces such as the Airflow webserver, Streamlit applications, and command-line tools enable orchestration, interaction, and consumption at the user level. As such, the figure complements the architectural description by showing how the chosen technologies are composed into a cohesive, end-to-end pipeline.

Figure 2: The 3PhaseInsight platform architecture, showing the current design choices

2.3 Data App Library

Data Apps are stored in a separate open-source framework, `3phi-framework`³, a Python library that provides the building blocks for the analytics programs' functionality. The `framework` implements a three-tier architecture: Data App, Controller, and Object-Relational Mapper, that enforces a clean separation of concerns and ensures all domain logic is consistently layered.

The framework abstracts object storage behind a common `BaseConnector` interface, with built-in implementations for both S3-compatible storage and Azure Blob Storage, making Data Apps agnostic to the popular cloud platforms. A `BaseDataApp` base class manages the Dask client lifecycle and exposes lazily-instantiated controllers, so Data Apps focus solely on their domain logic. The framework additionally provides workflow gating for whole-dataset steps, recording completion in a `meta.workflow_states` table to make pipelines safe to re-run without repeating work that has already been performed.

2.3.1 Controllers

The framework provides four controllers that sit between the Data Apps and the database resources. These modules, in essence, replace the functionality of the `Data Extractor` used in the `local prototyping environment`, as described in greater detail in D3.1 [3] and D3.2 [4]. Several controllers have been developed:

- The `TopologyController` manages the full lifecycle of LV network topology data: ingesting substation, transformer, feeder, cabinet, and meter assets into staging tables, running sanity checks, and atomically flipping a new versioned topology to current. It also exposes query methods to retrieve meters by substation, node, or transformer, and can export the topology back to the dataframe format used for ingestion.
- The `TimeSeriesController` provides processing-level-aware reads of smart meter time series data stored as partitioned Parquet files in object storage. Rather than maintaining multiple full copies of the data, it assembles the requested level at read time by merging the raw dataset with co-partitioned quality flags and corrections, and optionally applying a phase mapper to correct phase misassignment.
- The `MetaController` handles meter metadata and run results: it stores classifier output (data quality, statistics, connectivity) against individual meters, records workflow completion state to support idempotent pipeline re-runs, and provides flexible querying of `run_result` rows — the table that the API serves to external consumers.
- Finally, the `IngestionController` manages the ingestion batch lifecycle and file index, tracking which Parquet files have been written to object storage and atomically promoting a completed batch to ready.

2.3.2 Data Apps

Data Apps were initially developed in a `local prototyping environment` and progressively integrated into the `3PhaseInsight framework` as they matured. A complete inventory is provided in D1.1 [2], though not all modules were integrated during the project duration. The Data Apps described in D3.1 [3] and D3.2 [4] reflect the prototype environment; the following subsections describe their function and integration within the `framework` by the end of the project.

³<https://github.com/3PhaseInsight/3phi-framework>

Framework’s functional units: Functional units are the framework functionalities that prepare and structure data for downstream processing, rather than producing analytical results directly.

- **Time-series ingestor:** Reads raw smart meter measurements from CSV files and converts them into partitioned and sharded Parquet files stored in object storage. Partitioning by date and shard enables efficient distributed reads by downstream Data Apps. The ingestor is workflow-gated and skips execution if the workflow has already completed, unless `override` is set.
- **Topology ingestor:** Reads LV network topology and meter–cabinet mapping from CSV files and ingests them into the relational database. The ingestion pipeline loads data into staging tables, upserts all topology assets (substations, transformers, feeders, cabinets, delivery points, and meters), constructs the versioned node and edge graph, and atomically promotes the result to the current topology version. Like the time-series ingestor, it is workflow-gated.
- **Topology cleaner:** Reads the current topology version from the database, applies data-quality cleaning — including NaN imputation and duplicate edge removal — and re-ingests the result as a new topology version at processing level `CLEANED`. It is workflow-gated and skips if cleaning has already been performed on the current topology, unless `override` is set.

The described functional units are relevant to ensuring that the framework is loaded with the necessary dataset in the correct format to facilitate data analytics, which is to be performed by each data app. The data apps ported in the framework are described below:

- **Statistical Labeller:** Produces per-phase ground truth labels for electric heating by applying a Bayesian model comparison to each smart meter’s time series. Results are written per phase to `run_result` and serve as ground truth for the Electric Heating Identifier. The app is computationally intensive by design and intended to generate training labels rather than to run at scale in production.
- **Electric Heating Identifier:** Identifies smart meters with electric heating appliances by combining time-series feature engineering with semi-supervised machine learning. Using per-phase labels from `StatLabeller` as seeds for positive labels, and phases with no temperature correlation as negative labels, the algorithm propagates across the full feature space. The per-phase results are queried from `StatLabeller` by verifying the `workflow_states`. The result is a per-phase electric heating label with an associated confidence score, written back to `run_result`. Both the feature extraction and classification stages are workflow-gated per meter, so partially completed runs resume without reprocessing.
- **SM Classifier:** Evaluates smart meter time-series data to produce per-meter characterisation of data quality, statistical properties, and electrical connectivity. The app processes each meter independently, deriving phase-level indicators and aggregating them into structured outputs. Results are written to the platform’s metadata layer via the `MetaController`, updating the corresponding JSON fields in the `meta.meter` table. These outputs serve as a standardised schema for downstream Data Apps and provide a consistent interface for querying meter-level characteristics across the platform.
- **SM Phase Mapper:** Identifies the phase connectivity of smart meters within the LV network by combining time-series analysis with topology information. The app operates at the transformer level, retrieving meter–topology relationships via the `TopologyController` and time-series data through the `TimeSeriesController`. It further incorporates previously computed meter characterisation from the `MetaController`, particularly connectivity information, to guide the analysis. Results are written back to the metadata layer using the `MetaController`, where phase-mapping outputs are stored in a structured schema for each transformer. These results provide a consistent representation of inferred phase connectivity for use in downstream Data Apps and network analysis tasks.

-
- **Phase Connector:** Provides a service for recommending the optimal phase connection for a given smart meter and appliance type (heat pump, EV, or PV). The app combines topology information from the `TopologyController`, time-series data accessed via the `TimeSeriesController`, and previously computed labels retrieved through the `MetaController`, such as appliance predictions from upstream Data Apps. It computes a weighted scoring of candidate phases based on feeder-level balance, appliance distribution, and household consumption, and returns a ranked recommendation. The result is written to the `run_result` table, making it available through the platform API. Unlike batch-oriented Data Apps, the Phase Connector is designed to operate as an on-demand service, supporting interactive and decision-support use cases.

2.4 Flexible Deployment

The `data-platform` is designed to offer a high degree of deployment flexibility:

- **Database schema names:** the required tables must be present, but the schemas they are grouped under can be customised to fit existing naming conventions.
- **Object storage:** two object-storage technologies are supported out of the box, S3 and Azure Blob. An abstract `BaseConnector` defines the full storage interface, and both implementations are drop-in replacements for one another — Data Apps and controllers program only against this interface, so swapping the backend requires no application code changes. The same abstraction provides the foundation for adding support for further technologies with minimal effort.
- **Orchestration:** the default orchestration layer is Apache Airflow, but it can be replaced by any other orchestrator; the only requirement is a Python runtime to execute the Data Apps.
- **Scalability:** the Airflow worker and the Dask workers can each be scaled horizontally and vertically to match workload, cost and performance requirements.
- **Serverless execution:** because orchestration is decoupled from execution, the platform can target serverless backends on demand. Airflow can invoke serverless functions (AWS Lambda, Google Cloud Functions, Azure Functions) or run tasks on serverless containers (e.g. AWS Fargate, Google Cloud Run), so that only a lightweight, always-on Airflow instance is required while compute is provisioned per workflow. For compute-intensive Data Apps, serverless *containers* are the more natural fit, since true function-as-a-service imposes limits on execution time, memory, and state that such apps would need to adapt to.

2.5 Endpoints and Services

Data App results are exposed to external consumers through the platform's API, a FastAPI application that acts as the single, platform-agnostic egress point: consumers query it over standard HTTP and never access the database or object storage directly. Access is controlled by an API key passed in the `X-API-Key` header – a missing key is rejected with `401 Unauthorized` and an invalid one with `403 Forbidden`. As the API is built with FastAPI, an interactive OpenAPI (Swagger) specification is published automatically and serves as the contract for consumers. The current version (`v1`) provides an endpoint that returns the latest results a given Data App produced for a given meter:

```
GET /v1/data-apps/{data_app}/meters/{meter_id}/results/latest
```

The path parameters are:

- `data_app` – the Data App identifier. In `v1` this is the workflow's Airflow DAG id (e.g. `sm_classifier`); a friendlier alias layer is planned for a later version.
- `meter_id` – the meter the results are requested for.

The response is a JSON object containing the `data_app`, the `meter_id`, a `generated_at` timestamp (the time of the most recent underlying result), and a `results` array in which each entry reports:

- `phase` – the phase the result applies to;
- `label_type / label_value` – a typed, named result label;
- `confidence` – a confidence score for the result;
- `details` – an optional structured payload with additional, app-specific output.

If no results exist for the requested combination, the API responds with 404 Not Found.

Internally, the endpoint reads from the `run_result` table and returns the most recent run for the meter. Because every Data App writes to this uniform structure, further apps and endpoints can be served through the same response shape without bespoke per-app schemas.

Looking ahead, the API is expected to expose results not only at the meter level but also for the grid-graph entities (nodes, edges, and cables) that the `run_result` model already supports, and to replace its current static API key authentication with integration into *established authentication infrastructure for production deployments*.

3 Deployment and Showcasing

3.1 Radius Deployment

The deployment of the platform in a DSO environment, exemplified by the Radius setup, highlights the experience and challenges of integrating with existing DSO infrastructure. A typical DSO would likely have its own technology stack, deployed across different levels. The levels of expertise are also set to differ. Specifically, Radius typically relies on established software ecosystems for code development, pipeline execution, and data storage, which differ from the technologies used in the `3PhaseInsight` platform. As a result, introducing new components can require extensive approval processes due to IT security constraints, making full platform adoption non-trivial.

To address this, the `platform` architecture supports a *pick-and-choose* approach, allowing individual components to be integrated into existing environments. In the Radius deployment, this flexibility was realised by decoupling core functionality from platform-specific infrastructure. In particular, the abstraction of object storage behind the `BaseConnector` interface enables compatibility with different storage solutions without modifying application logic.

Rather than deploying the full orchestration stack, mainly the *framework* functionality was integrated into the existing Radius platform. However, few of the database components from the `data platform` were used in order to easily set up databases in the existing environment. Data Apps were executed directly within the host environment, relying on the required data formats and schemas while leveraging Radius's own infrastructure for scheduling and execution. This approach reduces the integration burden while still enabling advanced analytics and data processing capabilities.

The deployment demonstrates two viable modes of operation: using the full platform as a standalone system or selectively integrating its components into existing environments. The latter is particularly suited to organisations with established infrastructure, as it allows them to extend their capabilities without replacing existing systems.

In Figure 3, an overview of Radius' deployment architecture for the `platform` is shown. This demonstrates the path from the source file in CSV format to the bucket storage format in their Azure environment, then processing with the Data App framework itself, and finally monitoring results in the PostgreSQL schemas and executing Data Apps from the terminal.

Figure 3: Pipeline infrastructure of Radius' solution with the Data Platform.

3.2 Phase Connection Assistant

The Phase Connection Assistant is an application-level service built on top of multiple Data Apps to provide actionable recommendations for phase allocation of new electrical appliances. It combines outputs from upstream analytics with topology and time-series data to deliver decision support for grid operation. See more details in D1.1 [2].

- **Pipeline composition:** The assistant orchestrates a sequence of Data Apps, namely the Statistical Labeler, the Electric Heating Identifier, and the Phase Connector. These are executed in a coordinated workflow to ensure that all required intermediate results (e.g. ground-truth labels and appliance predictions) are available before phase recommendation is performed.
- **Integration of platform components:** The service leverages the framework controllers to interact with the platform layers: topology information is retrieved through the `TopologyController`, time-series data through the `TimeSeriesController`, and intermediate as well as final results through the `MetaController`. This ensures that all computations are performed on consistent, centrally managed data representations.
- **Execution model:** The assistant is implemented as an Apache Airflow DAG, where a single task triggers the service logic. Within this task, the Data Apps are executed sequentially using the framework runtime. This design enables reproducible execution, integration into larger workflows, and optional scheduling in production deployments.
- **Dynamic dependency resolution:** Prior to computing the final recommendation, the service ensures that all prerequisite results exist. If necessary, upstream Data Apps (e.g. label generation) are triggered for all smart meters within the same feeder, ensuring completeness of input data.

- **Scope of computation:** The assistant operates at the feeder level, first identifying all smart meters connected to the same feeder as the target meter and then aggregating their data to evaluate phase balance and appliance distribution.
- **Outputs:** The final output is a ranked recommendation of phases (L1, L2, L3) for connecting a new appliance, together with detailed scoring metrics. Results are written to the `run_result` table via the `MetaController`, making them accessible through the platform API. Optional visualisations and diagnostics may be stored in object storage.
- **Service-oriented usage:** Unlike standalone Data Apps, the Phase Connection Assistant is designed for on-demand execution, enabling interactive decision-support use cases such as planning tools or operator interfaces. Its encapsulation as a single DAG task allows it to function both as part of scheduled workflows and as a callable service.
- **Current scope and extensions:** The current implementation focuses on heat pump (HP) scenarios, where upstream appliance identification is available through the Electric Heating Identifier. Support for electric vehicle (EV) and photovoltaic (PV) scenarios, present in the prototype environment, is planned but not yet fully integrated into the platform framework.

3.3 Web Service with Streamlit

To make the Data Apps accessible without requiring direct interaction with the Airflow interface or command-line tooling, a Streamlit-based web application was developed as a lightweight showcase and operational interface. The application provides a unified entry point for configuring and executing Data Apps and for inspecting their results through a browser-based UI that requires no platform-specific knowledge from the user. This interface is developed only as an example, and DSOs or other stakeholders can determine themselves which elements are important.

The interface is structured around a shared navigation sidebar from which the operator selects the Data App to interact with. A shared **data directory path** is configurable across all apps, and each app exposes only the configuration parameters essential to its execution. Once configured, apps are triggered directly from the interface via a run button, and results are presented in the UI, with progress shown inline.

Figure 4: Streamlit Dashboard showing an overview of the dataset contained in the framework

The following Data Apps are currently exposed through the web service:

- **Data Explorer:** Provides an inventory overview of what data is available in the framework: metadata loaded in the database and raw Parquet files available in object storage. For a given topology version, it reports the number of meters in the database, meters with data quality,

statistics, and connectivity characterisations, the number of raw Parquet files, and the LV topology inventory including substations, transformers, feeders, cabinets, delivery points, and cables. It serves as a first point of inspection before running any analytical Data App.

- **Ingestors:** Exposes the time-series or topology ingestion pipeline, allowing the operator to specify a CSV source folder, a file pattern, and a Parquet destination. An override flag and a worker count are also configurable. The app converts raw smart meter CSV measurements into partitioned Parquet datasets in object storage. For the topology CSV, the information is ingested into the appropriate PostgreSQL schemas.

Figure 5: Interface for time-series ingestion

Figure 6: Interface for topology ingestion

- **SM Classifier:** Allows the operator to review existing classifier outputs and, when needed, trigger a new classification run over a configurable sample of smart meters. Results are browsable across three tabs — *Classification*, *Characterization*, and *Smart meter plots* — with filtering by meter scope, characterisation section, phase, and variable. Summary metrics (meters in run, data-quality counts, connection errors, and on/off-switch counts) are displayed at the top of the results view.

Figure 7: Smart Meter Classifier interface

- **Stat Labeler:** Supports running the statistical heat-pump labelling algorithm and inspecting its outputs. Results from a selected run are summarised by the number of meters evaluated, HP-positive meters, and total HP-positive phases, together with per-phase bar charts of heat-pump detections.

Figure 8: Statistical Labeler results interface

Figure 9: Statistical Labeler results showcased

The Streamlit application therefore serves a dual purpose: as a *showcase* that demonstrates platform capabilities to stakeholders, and as a lightweight *operational interface* for executing and inspecting Data Apps without requiring access to the Airflow webserver or the underlying infrastructure.

3.4 Interoperability and Validation

A guiding principle of the platform is interoperability without vendor lock-in, and this holds at two levels. At the **platform level**, the containerised deployment is portable across environments: the object-storage backend is pluggable behind an abstract connector, the orchestration layer can be substituted (only a Python runtime is required to execute the Data Apps), and the database schema names are configurable to fit existing conventions. At the **data-exchange level**, ingestion is handled through interchangeable adapters, time-series data is kept in an open columnar format, and results are exposed through a single, documented API.

The consumer-facing interfaces are deliberately open and platform-agnostic: the API is a standard authenticated HTTP endpoint over the `run_result` table that any conforming client can query, independent of how or where the platform is deployed. Together with the pluggable connectors and configurable storage, this keeps both the data and its consumers free of platform-specific assumptions.

These properties were validated by deploying the platform across three distinct environments:

- **Local** – a self-contained local setup used during development.
- **Cloud VM** – a deployment on a virtual machine on DigitalOcean, tested end to end.
- **Partner environment** – an instance adapted and deployed by Radius within their own infrastructure.

Running the platform unchanged in the first two settings and in an adapted form in the third demonstrates its portability and the absence of lock-in in practice. The Radius deployment is particularly relevant to the data-ownership goal: the platform runs on the data owner's own infrastructure, so the data need not leave their environment.

Validation at this stage focused on deployability and interoperability across environments rather than on performance at full data volume, which is left to future work.

The partner deployment surfaced a practical lesson. The platform is built entirely on open-source technologies by design—a deliberate choice supporting data sovereignty and avoiding proprietary lock-in. In tightly governed environments, however, every technology must still pass an internal approval (whitelisting) process; the main effort in the Radius deployment was getting the PostgreSQL database approved rather than any technical integration. To keep the footprint minimal, Radius omitted Airflow: instead of the orchestration layer, Data Apps are triggered directly from the host via the

`execute_data_app.sh` launcher with the appropriate environment variables, and computation runs on a single-machine Dask cluster rather than a distributed one.

Rather than a limitation, this illustrates the breadth of the platform's deployment spectrum: the same codebase runs from a fully orchestrated, horizontally scaled cluster down to a minimal single-machine setup with no orchestration layer. It is also concrete evidence for two of the design properties stated above—that the orchestration layer is replaceable (only a Python runtime is needed to run the Data Apps) and that compute scales from a single machine to a distributed cluster. The trade-off is that the minimal setup forgoes Airflow's scheduling, monitoring and DAG chaining as well as distributed scaling, making it well suited to smaller-scale or strictly governed environments rather than large, scheduled pipelines.

4 Conclusion and future cases

The 3PhaseInsight open-source data platform demonstrates that LV grid analytics can be delivered on a portable, self-hostable stack built entirely from open-source components. The platform ingests time-series and topology data through interchangeable adapters, runs analytical Data Apps as orchestrated workflows on a scalable compute layer, and exposes results through a single documented API — all while keeping data on the owner's own infrastructure. Its design was validated across three distinct environments, from a self-contained local setup to a partner deployment adapted by Radius, confirming portability and the absence of vendor lock-in in practice. The same codebase runs from a fully orchestrated, horizontally scaled cluster down to a minimal single-machine setup, making the platform suitable across a broad range of deployment contexts, governance constraints and workflows. The remainder of this section outlines the principal directions for building on this foundation, together with the limitations observed during the project.

4.1 Data-Space-Compliant Deployment

A natural future direction is to operate the platform as a participant in a data space, in line with the emerging Common European Data Spaces⁴, and the energy data space⁵ in particular. The platform already satisfies the central prerequisite of these initiatives, data sovereignty: it is self-hostable and keeps data on the data owner's own infrastructure, as demonstrated by the Radius deployment, where the data never leaves their environment. Building on this, a data-space-compliant deployment would share results through a data-space *connector* - a standardised component that exchanges data directly between participants under explicit, agreed usage policies - rather than through the current open API alone.

Two of the platform's current limitations map onto what such a deployment requires. First, **authentication**: the present static API-key scheme would give way to the data space's shared identity and trust framework, in which participants are identified and authorised according to policies agreed for each exchange, rather than through keys managed by the platform itself. Second, the **way results are shared**: the platform's existing pluggable-connector pattern, already used for object storage, lends itself to adding such a data-space connector alongside the existing API. Together these would let data owners share Data App results on their own terms within a trusted, interoperable ecosystem - turning the platform's data-ownership and open-interface principles into formal data-space compliance.

4.2 Continuous Ingestion

The platform was designed for continuous operation, but validation within the project used a static historical dataset. A natural next step is to exercise the ingestion path in streaming mode, where new smart meter measurements arrive continuously rather than as a single bulk load. The architecture already accommodates this: ingestion runs as a scheduled Airflow DAG, the adapter pattern abstracts the data source, and the workflow-gating mechanism in `meta.workflow_states` makes repeated runs idempotent. Moving to continuous ingestion would mainly involve scheduling the ingestion DAGs at the cadence at which data becomes available and extending the workflow-gating logic to operate incrementally — processing only newly arrived partitions rather than re-evaluating the whole dataset. This would also surface operational questions left untested under batch conditions, such as late-arriving or corrected measurements, partition compaction, and how downstream Data Apps are retriggered as their inputs grow.

⁴<https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/data-spaces>

⁵https://energy.ec.europa.eu/publications/common-european-energy-data-space_en

4.3 Limitations

The platform described in this report is a research prototype, and several limitations of the current implementation should be read alongside the design above.

Deployment and operations: The system runs as a single-node container stack without high availability, continuous integration, monitoring, alerting, automated backups, or managed secrets; credentials are committed only as local-development defaults and must be replaced for any real deployment.

Modelling assumptions: The analyses assume a three-phase supply and a radial low-voltage grid. This keeps the topology and phase logic tractable, but networks with a different phase arrangement or with meshed, non-radial connectivity fall outside what the current implementation can represent and process.

Analytics: The classification and labelling algorithms were developed against smart-meter data at fifteen-minute resolution. In real-world deployments data at this granularity may not be available, so the algorithms may need to be adapted - for instance to coarser sampling intervals or to incomplete measurement records - before they can be applied more broadly.

Scalability and interfaces: The platform does not scale automatically: the data is split into a fixed number of partitions, some processing steps must hold an entire dataset in memory at once, and the amount of compute is fixed in advance, so the volume of data it can process is capped by these static choices. Because storage is already decoupled from compute and distributed processing is in place, these constraints can be relaxed incrementally—by re-partitioning, by streaming the affected steps, and by scaling the compute cluster—without reworking the platform as a whole. The orchestrated pipelines are manually triggered single-task workflows without retries or scheduling, the customer-facing API so far exposes only a single read endpoint and is not yet complete, and automated test coverage of the domain logic remains limited.

5 References

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- [2] 3PhaseInsight Consortium. Use cases for data apps and data pipelines, June 2026. URL <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20793151>.
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- [4] 3PhaseInsight Consortium. Deliverable D3.2: Description of implemented data app algorithms, June 2026. URL <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.21072394>.
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Appendix: Definition of terms

Alias(es)	Meaning	Named Location
<i>data app</i>	Functional data processing unit, based on configuration, input and output formats.	concept originated in project proposal
<i>data pipeline</i>	Conceptual sequence of data apps to generate insights and services	concept originated in project proposal
<i>service</i>	User-facing endpoint of a data pipeline, including a graphical user interface with functionality to query precomputed results and potentially an interaction mechanisms to configure and trigger data pipeline execution. Endpoint may have varied security privileges, including public-facing endpoints.	concept originated in project proposal
Energidata.dk (<i>EDDK</i>)	Platform to host open and protected data from the Danish energy system as well as data from several "living labs" and research projects. Here it is used to create a protected and maintainable data host.	Energidata.dk entrypoint: Dataset "3PhaseInsightProject"
<i>local prototyping environment</i>	Initial Python development platform for data apps and data pipelines, developed at DTU. It was developed to formalize the data app concept and allows rapid prototyping and HPC compatible deployment of data apps. Implemented with pure file-based data storage and access. No data-versioning.	Contact DTU authors for access.
<i>cloud-compatible platform</i>	A cloud-compatible open-source platform developed by INILAB to enable professional and scalable data handling and deployment of data apps, comprising the 3PhaseInsight <i>framework</i> (<i>3phi-framework</i>) and the <i>data platform</i> .	3PhaseInsight at GitHub
3PhaseInsight <i>framework</i>	The core interoperable data app framework, which defines the core libraries and connectors and contains the code for available data apps. provides REST endpoints	3phi-framework
<i>data platform</i>	An open-source modular platform containing necessary components to spin up functionalities given by the <i>framework</i>	data-platform
<i>DAG</i>	an A workflow definition that specifies a set of tasks and their dependencies, providing the mechanism to schedule, trigger and monitor the execution of one or more Data Apps within the platform. A DAG can specify a single Data App or a entire data pipeline.	part of data-platform
<i>endpoint, API</i>	A single addressable route on the platform's HTTP API through which an external consumer retrieves a specific Data App's results over standard HTTP. The API itself is FastAPI application that serves as the single egress point through which external consumers query Data App results.	data-platform-api, part of data-platform
API	Customer-facing HTTP API for the 3PhaseInsight Data Platform.	data-platform-api, part of data-platform

Table 1: Terminology mapping. Preferred aliases are shown in italics.

Consortium

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